

KKNI-BASED ISLAMIC RELIGIOUS EDUCATION CURRICULUM MANAGEMENT IN INCREASING GRADUATE COMPETENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

The IQF has a function as a minimum frame of reference that serves as a measure, recognition of the educational attainment being carried out. The curriculum determines the range of competencies to be achieved from an educational/learning process, although it is not the only determinant, given the many supporting conditions that need attention. The aim of the study is to obtain an overview of the management of the Islamic religious education curriculum based on the Indonesian National Qualifications Framework in increasing the competency of graduates in higher education. The research method is a case study, as well as data collection techniques through interviews, documentation and observation. The foundation of curriculum theory, from Sukmadinata, the results of this study confirm that in management theory, as a good learning planning system, the curriculum must include four things. First, the final results of education that students must achieve (output), and are formulated as graduate competencies. Second, the content of the material to be taught and studied by students (content standards), in an effort to form the desired graduate competencies. Third, the implementation of learning (process), including learning methodology as part of the standard process, so that the three competencies desired in students are formed. Fourth, evaluate the suitability of the process and the achievement of learning objectives that are applied as early as possible to ensure that inputs, processes and outputs are according to plan. Conclusion STAI Yamisa and STAI Darul Falah implement an IQF-based curriculum, namely: formulation of curriculum objectives, identification of curriculum sources, curriculum organization and structure, learning strategies and methods, development of professional capabilities, scheduling of lecture activities, supporting elements, coaching systems, process evaluation curriculum. Value of Novelty: Hypothetical Model of Curriculum Management for Bachelor of Islamic Education Study Program

Keywords: Management, IQF, Competence.

INTRODUCTION

With the IQF perspective, each study program is required to clarify the expected "graduate profile" through study tracking activities, feasibility studies and needs analysis in the community. The graduate profile reflects the minimum abilities that students must master after graduation which refers to four aspects of needs (1) attitude, (2) work ability, (3) knowledge, and (4) managerial and responsibility. Furthermore, these four abilities must be translated into a learning outcome for each subject in the study program. So that

later, all learning plans or Semester Implementation Plans (RPS) must be based on learning outcomes (Learning Outcomes) that suit the needs of graduate profiles.

However, this has not been implemented optimally in PTKIS, even though Kopertais has conducted various coaching and training such as seminars/workshops/training for PTKIS leaders in implementing the KKNI-based PT curriculum policy.

This condition occurs, perhaps due to the lack of ability of the leaders to understand the foundation of education, the weakening of the spirit of educating, and the not yet optimal in carrying out their professional duties, besides that the subject matter taught is not in accordance with their educational background, there is still a lack of awareness of lecturers in the use of teaching time effectively. Effective, as well as implementation in the field that is not in accordance with the plans that have been designed.

RESEARCH METHODS

The method used in this research is descriptive with a case study type. The reason for using this method is because this method has two main objectives, namely first to describe and reveal (to describe and explore) and secondly to describe and explain (to describe and explain). The research attempts to describe and analyze the real conditions in several tertiary institutions regarding the implementation of the IQF-based Islamic Religious Education curriculum in Islamic Religious Education (PAI) study programs in depth.

RESEARCH RESULT

1. Planning

a. Formulation of the objectives of the IQF-based Islamic Religious Education curriculum

Based on the results of interviews, observations, and documentation, information was obtained that the formulation of the objectives of the STAI Yamisa PAI study program consisted of general goals and specific goals.

The general objective refers to the documents contained in the law. No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, UU. No. 12 of 2012 concerning Higher Education, Presidential Decree no. 8 of 2012 concerning KKNI, Permenristekdikti No. 50 of 2018. Meanwhile, the specific goals are directed at forming educational scholars who are experts in Islamic religious knowledge (*mutafaqqih fid din*).

The profile of graduates of the Bachelor of Islamic Education Study Program is determined through a mechanism for combining academic visions which is carried out by combining academic visions which is carried out by SWOT analysis (Strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) and analysis of market needs through tracer studies of alumni and also input from professional associations, stakeholders and the community (student guardians).

b. Identification of IQF Based Islamic Religious Education Curriculum Sources

Based on the results of interviews, observations, and documentation, information was obtained that the identification of sources for the IQF-Based Islamic Religious Education curriculum adheres to a legal basis

2. Execution

a. Strategy and learning method of IQF-Based Islamic Religious Education

Based on the results of interviews, observations, and documentation, information was obtained that the learning strategy carried out by the PAI STAI Yamisa Study Program was subject-based or student-centered learning (SCL) courses.

In implementing this model there are several steps that need to be considered, namely: (1) creating a network of courses; (2) Each course is made a semester learning plan (RPS); (3) Each lecturer makes a lesson plan.

b. Professional Capability Development

Based on the results of interviews, observations, and documentation, information was obtained that the development of professional skills was carried out by mapping areas of expertise or lecturer expertise, research activities, dissemination of journals, and training/workshops.

c. Scheduling Lecture Activities

Based on the results of interviews, observations, and documentation, information was obtained that the academic calendar of the PAI STAI Yamisa Study Program was prepared for 1 academic year with reference to efficiency, effectiveness and students' rights. The academic calendar contains hours of effective time used for teaching and learning activities, study evaluation time, and holiday time. The academic calendar is then elaborated by each teaching team lecturer in order to arrange a schedule of lecture activities

d. Supporting Elements in Implementing the IQF-based Islamic Religious Education Curriculum

In general, the facilities owned by STAI Yamisa that support tri dharma activities include building facilities intended for CBT buildings and halls, rectorate rooms, classes, micro teaching laboratories, languages, study program rooms, archive rooms, BAAK rooms, career and entrepreneurship center rooms, UKS room, LPMP room and LPPM room. With a total of 16 classrooms, 12 classes for the PAI undergraduate study program, 4 classes for the HES study program, with an area of 76 m² per class, and a library room that has an area of 174 m².

As for infrastructure that supports educational activities, namely parking lots, sports fields: basketball, volleyball, futsal, badminton, buses and mini buses, health clinics. While the Information Technology system owned: Academic and Student Affairs information system (SIAK), Financial Information System (SIMKEU), Personnel Information System (SIMPEG), Inventory system, Cash Management System (CMS), Electronic Library

System, Digital Library, Quality Assurance System Internal, New Student Admission System, E-journal, E-learning, Bank information system and evaluation of questions (SIBANES).

3. Evaluation

Based on the results of interviews, observations, and documentation, information was obtained that the process evaluation carried out by the STAI Yamisa PAI study program included: evaluation of lesson plans, evaluation of teaching and learning activities (presence of lecturers and students), assessment of learning (at the end of each semester and at the end of the education program).

DISCUSSION

1. Planning

a. Formulation of the objectives of the IQF-based Islamic Religious Education curriculum

Objectives play an important role, because they direct all teaching activities and color other curriculum components. Curriculum objectives are formulated based on two things, namely the development of demands, needs and conditions of society, and are based on thoughts and are directed at achieving philosophical values, especially the philosophy of the state. On a macro scale, the formulation of curriculum objectives is closely related to the philosophy or value system adopted by society. In fact, the formulation of objectives describes an aspired society. On a micro scale, curriculum objectives relate to the mission and vision of educational levels as well as narrower objectives, such as the objectives of each subject and the objectives of the learning process.

b. Identification of IQF Based Islamic Religious Education Curriculum Sources

Identification of curriculum resources has a very important role. If the curriculum is likened to a building that does not use a strong foundation or foundation, then when it is hit by wind or shaking, the building will easily collapse. Likewise with the curriculum, if it does not have a strong foundation, then the curriculum will be easily swayed and what will be at stake are the humans (students) produced by the education itself.

c. Organization and Structure of the IQF-Based Islamic Religious Education Curriculum

Curriculum organization is a pattern or design of curriculum materials whose purpose is to make it easier for students to learn subject matter and make it easier for students to carry out learning activities so that learning objectives can be achieved effectively. Curriculum organization is closely related to the arrangement of learning materials in the curriculum, while the sources of learning materials in the curriculum are cultural values, social values, aspects of students and society, as well as science and technology. There are several factors that must be considered in curriculum organization, including those related to scope, sequence, continuity, balance, and integration. In the undergraduate curriculum organization of Islamic Religious Education Study Program, the curriculum is

based on the Indonesian National Qualifications Framework (KKNI) which includes attitudes and values, knowledge/scientific mastery, general work skills, special work skills, which are divided into the core curriculum and institutional curriculum.

Execution

a. Strategy and learning method of IQF-Based Islamic Religious Education

Learning strategies have a very important role because they relate to curriculum implementation. However good and ideally the goal must be achieved without the right strategy to achieve it, then the goal is impossible to achieve. Learning strategy can be interpreted as an action plan (series of activities) including the use of methods and utilization of various resources/strengths in learning. This means that the preparation of a new strategy has not yet reached the process of preparing a work plan. The learning strategy can also be interpreted as the direction of all strategy-making decisions is the attainment of goals. Thus, the preparation of learning steps, the use of various facilities and learning resources are all directed towards achieving goals.

The learning strategy carried out by the PAI Undergraduate Study Program is subject-based or student-centered learning (SCL). This is in line with the results of Purwadhi's research (2019: 143), which reveals:

The 21 st century learning includes: firstly, learning development uses learning approach that is centered to students; secondly, students must have studied to be able to collaborate with others; thirdly, subject matter needs to be related to students' daily life; and fourthly, school should facilitate students to be involved in their social environment.

b. Professional Capability Development

To implement the curriculum in accordance with the design, it takes some readiness, especially the readiness of implementers. No matter how good the curriculum design is, if it is not supported by professional teaching staff (lecturers), then the curriculum design is only a pseudo-document. Even a simple curriculum, if the lecturer has the ability, enthusiasm, and high dedication, the results will be better than a good curriculum design. Lecturers are the main key to successful curriculum implementation. Other educational resources such as infrastructure, costs, organization, environment, are also the keys to educational success, but the main key is the lecturers. With limited facilities, infrastructure and costs, lecturers who are creative and highly dedicated can develop innovative programs, activities and learning aids. For this reason, it is necessary to develop the professionalism of lecturers with various programs that can lead to this goal.

c. Scheduling Lecture Activities

Academic calendar is a general term in the world of education that refers to the annual schedule of activities of an educational institution which contains all matters related to the teaching and learning process, student admissions, and graduation. This academic calendar is arranged in a pattern that describes the duration and types of academic activities.

The academic calendar of the PAI study program is prepared for 1 academic year by referring to the efficiency, effectiveness and rights of students. The academic calendar contains hours of effective time used for teaching and learning activities, study evaluation time, and holiday time. From a theoretical point of view, STAI Yamisa and STAI Darul Falah are in line with the concept of the educational calendar itself which is "time setting for student learning activities for one school year which includes the beginning of the school year, effective week of learning, effective learning time, and holidays." (Triwiyanto, 2015: 125).

An institution can compile an educational calendar according to regional needs, campus characteristics, the needs of students and the community by taking into account the educational calendar as contained in the content standards. With the educational calendar, learning activities are expected to run effectively and efficiently.

d. Supporting Elements in Implementing the IQF-based Islamic Religious Education Curriculum

Supporting elements are one component that helps in the educational process. Learning support elements are none other than resources that can be utilized for the benefit of the teaching and learning process, either directly or indirectly, in part or as a whole. These supporting elements can be said to be everything that exists around the learning activity environment which functionally can be used to help optimize learning outcomes.

Optimization of these learning outcomes can be seen not only from the learning outcomes (output) but also seen from the process in the form of student interaction with various sources that can stimulate learning and accelerate understanding and mastery of the fields of knowledge they are studying. Supporting elements in the educational process at both STAIs consist of facilities, infrastructure, and information technology systems.

3. Evaluation

Curriculum evaluation is intended to check the level of achievement of educational goals to be realized through the relevant curriculum. The work indicator to be evaluated is program effectiveness. In a broad sense, curriculum evaluation is intended to check the performance of the curriculum as a whole in terms of various criteria. The performance indicators evaluated are program effectiveness, relevance, efficiency, and feasibility.

The evaluation in the curriculum development process is intended to improve the program in the future, form accountability to various parties, and determine the follow-up results of development. The process evaluation carried out by the Bachelor of Islamic Education Study Program includes: evaluation of lesson plans, evaluation of teaching and learning activities (attendance of lecturers and students), Assessment of learning (at the end of each semester and at the end of the education program).

4. Follow Up

The follow-up/coaching system is an activity carried out in order to improve the quality of education for health workers which is carried out in a planned, continuous, sustainable and open manner.

This activity covers the administrative and technical aspects of education with the aim that the institution is responsible for the implementation of educational activities and continues to provide continuous guidance, in the sense of trying to ensure that the management, assessment, guidance, insight and development of education can be carried out properly.

Coaching is an assistance effort given by lecturers to students, senior lecturers to juniors, heads to education staff and education staff. In the guidance system applied to the PAI undergraduate study program, namely: supervision, accreditation, evaluation of education implementation, monitoring and evaluation of lecturers.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

1. Conclusion

a. Planning

The formulation of the objectives of the IQF-based Islamic Religious Education curriculum consists of general objectives and specific objectives, Identification of the sources of the IQF-based Islamic Religious Education curriculum adhering to the legal basis, Organization and structure of the IQF-based Islamic Religious Education curriculum includes attitudes and values, mastery of knowledge/scientific , general work skills, specific work skills, which are divided into the core curriculum and the institutional curriculum;

b. Implementation

The IQF-based Islamic Religious Education learning strategy and method is subject-based or student-centered learning (SCL). Professional capability development is carried out by mapping areas of expertise or lecturer expertise, research activities, dissemination of journals, and training/ workshops, scheduling of lecture activities is prepared for 1 academic year with reference to efficiency, effectiveness and the rights of students. Supporting elements in implementing the IQF-based Islamic Religious Education curriculum consist of facilities, infrastructure, and information technology systems;

c. Evaluation

The IQF-based Islamic Religious Education curriculum process includes: evaluation of lesson plans, evaluation of teaching and learning activities (attendance of lecturers and students), assessment of learning (at the end of each semester and at the end of educational programs).

d. Follow-up

The IQF-based Islamic Religious Education curriculum development system includes: supervision, accreditation, evaluation of education implementation, monitoring and evaluation of lecturers;

2. Suggestion

Based on several field findings, the researcher proposes the following suggestions:

1) College Manager

STAI Yamisa and STAI Darul Falah need to take concrete steps in order to develop and manage a quality nursing curriculum as follows:

- a) Conduct a thorough evaluation of the management of the Islamic Religious Education curriculum, starting from the process of planning, organizing, implementing, and evaluating the curriculum. This is done to find out the weak points of the institution in managing the curriculum;
- b) Empowering curriculum development teams to design superior emergency curricula that suit the needs of future students in society;
- c) Higher education administrators pay attention to the skills and competencies of teaching staff in order to improve the competence of students;
- d) Pay attention to supporting facilities and infrastructure;
- e) Expanding cooperation with users to explore potential in the financial sector.

2) Lecturer

There is no uniform understanding of the curriculum so that there are differences in readiness and treatment in learning management. On that basis, it is necessary to have a special mentoring and assistance program for the lecturers who are directly involved to understand deeply and completely, especially regarding methods, media and approaches, as well as the developed curriculum.

3) Policy Holders within the Ministry of Religion

To improve the quality of learning at Islamic Religious Colleges (PTKI) in the case of Kopertais, it is necessary to do the following:

- a) Intensive or periodic coaching to tertiary institutions related to the implementation of the IQF-based curriculum;
- b) Support morally and morally in fulfilling the supporting elements of lecture activities.

4) Other researchers

The presence of tertiary institutions that organize Bachelor of Islamic Education study programs makes a major contribution in providing religious and educational services to the community. However, in reality in the field, there are still many problems that stakeholders (policy makers) must immediately find solutions to, starting from the macro level (central government), meso (local government), and micro (educational units). Therefore, other studies are needed in order to provide solutions to the educational problems that occur in the PAI undergraduate study program.

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